

Proof of Legendre's Conjecture

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July 2, 2024

Abstract

Legendre's conjecture is proved to be true.

1 Introduction

Legendre's conjecture is as following[Bazzanella(2000)]:

Does there always exist at least one prime between n^2 and $(n+1)^2$?

2 Proof

Upper statement gets true if $n \in \mathbb{N}$ with any $2n+1$ period starting from n^2 has at least one prime in itself. By the definition of generalized prime number sequence[Yoon(2023)]:

$$p = (t^3 + 3t^2 + 2t)p' + p''$$

with $p, p', p'' \in \mathbb{P}, t \in \mathbb{N}$.

$$\begin{aligned} p - p'' &= (t^3 + 3t^2 + 2t)p' \\ (p'')^2 &= (p - (t^3 + 3t^2 + 2t)p')^2 \\ (p'' + 1)^2 &= (p - (t^3 + 3t^2 + 2t)p' + 1)^2 \\ (p'' + 1)^2 - (p'')^2 &= 2(p - (t^3 + 3t^2 + 2t)p') + 1 \end{aligned}$$

with $t \in \mathbb{N}$ exists for $2(p - (t^3 + 3t^2 + 2t)p') + 1$ being less than $2p'' + 1$ with arbitrary p, p', p'' , then Legendre's conjecture gets true. For least case with $p = 5, p' = 2, p'' = 3$ then $t = 1$ and $2(p - (t^3 + 3t^2 + 2t)p') + 1 \leq 2p'' + 1$ gets true. So Legendre's conjecture is true.

References

- [Bazzanella(2000)] D. Bazzanella. Primes between consecutive squares. *Archiv der Mathematik*, 75(1):29–34, July 2000. ISSN 1420-8938. doi: 10.1007/s000130050469. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s000130050469>.
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